

Short communication

First report of *Scolothrips dilongicornis* (Thys.: Thripidae) from Iran

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چکیده

در بررسی فونستیک بال‌ریشک‌داران استان خراسان رضوی طی سال‌های ۱۳۹۱-۹۲، نمونه‌هایی متعلق به گونه *Scolothrips dilongicornis* Han & Zhang, 1982 جمع‌آوری و شناسایی شد. این گونه برای اولین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شود و به این ترتیب تعداد گونه‌های جنس *Scolothrips* Hinds در ایران به چهار عدد می‌رسد.

During the faunistic survey of thrips (Thysanoptera) in Khorasan-e Razavi province from 2012 through 2013, several thripid specimens of the genus *Scolothrips* Hinds were collected and later identified as *Scolothrips dilongicornis* Hang & Zhang using the key by Mound (2011). The members of this genus are predators of mites on plant leaves (Gilstrap, 1995).

The genus *Scolothrips* is easily identified by the presence of six (rarely five) pairs of long setae on the pronotum and a similar pair between the ocelli. But the identification of its species has remained difficult (Bhatti *et al.*, 2009; Mound, 2011).

- *Scolothrips dilongicornis* Hang & Zhang, 1982

Material examined – 6 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, IRAN: Khorasan-e Razavi province, Mashhad, 20.x.2012, leg. L. Fekrat.

Diagnosis – This species belongs to the *longicornis* species-group, which currently contains three described species, viz. *S. dilongicornis*, *S. longicornis* Priesner, and *S. takahashii* Priesner. These species cannot be distinguished from each other satisfactorily and male

specimens must be available for positive species identification. Males of *S. longicornis* and *S. takahashii* are hemimacropterous and macropterous respectively, while the males of *S. dilongicornis* are micropterous (Mound, 2011).

Scolothrips dilongicornis, which is newly reported from Iran, was originally described from China (Hang & Zhang, 1982). Three species of *Scolothrips*, *S. latipennis* Priesner, *S. longicornis*, *S. rhagebianus* Priesner, have hitherto been reported from Iran (Bhatti *et al.*, 2009) and thereby, the total Iranian recorded species of this genus increases to four species. It is worth mentioning that the occurrence of *Scolothrips sexmaculatus* (Pergande) in Iran, as firstly reported by Shishehbor (1991), was not accepted due to being not authentically determined (Bhatti *et al.*, 2009).

The specimens are deposited at the Thysanoptera collection of the Hayk Mirzayans Insect Museum, Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection, Tehran, Iran.

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